

Problems arising during transportation of Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids and their solutions

Farida Bagisheva

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5457-7863>, farida.bagisheva.std@bhos.edu.az

Khanim Abasova

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9491-1433>, khanim.abasova.std@bhos.edu.az

Melahet Aliyeva

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6747-6994>, malahat.aliyeva.std@bhos.edu.az

Aisha Muradzade

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7702-6566>, aisha.muradzade.std@bhos.edu.az

Petroleum Engineering Department, Baku Higher Oil School, Azerbaijan

Khanim Abasova: abasovaxanim503@gmail.com, +994705874134

Supervisors: Aida Aslanova, Qahraman Melikov

Abstract:

The main purpose of this thesis is to research the problems created by Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids in the petroleum transportation and bring an innovation to the solution of these problems. The supplied material gives information about solution method: viscosity blending. The method is based on adding light oil to heavy one in a certain concentration to decrease its viscosity. The advantages and disadvantages of this method in solving problems have been specially compared in the discussion section. An experiment was conducted to investigate and confirm the viscosity blending method, and the result of the experiment proves that the method is effective. In order to bring innovation to the method, it is offered to use biofuel instead of light oil. Certain experimental studies have been conducted to confirm this offer. The offer is aimed at solving the problems that arise during the transportation of fluids in the petroleum industry.

Keywords: viscosity blending, eco-friendly, biofuel, transportation.

Introduction:

Non-newtonian fluids in petroleum industry, causes some problems during the transportation of hydrocarbons. Viscosity or pressure drop is one of them. If flow rate is low some types of non-newtonian fluids, especially shear-thickening or viscoplastic, possess very high viscosity leading to losses in pressure, which in turn increases energy costs. (Schlumberger, 2016) To transport cement slurries or heavy hydrocarbons certain force should be applied to overcome yield stress that they own. It is not desirable, since delays and blockages can happen due to this problem. (Dong, 2012) In addition, non-newtonian fluids present in petroleum industry are reactive to temperature. It means their viscosity increase as temperature goes down. During production, the bottom hole pressure decreases and this causes the viscosity of the well fluid to change. This condition can cause problems such as decline and clogging in the pipeline, it can lead changes in flow efficiency and EOR. (Ahmed, 2019)

In the petroleum industry, there are problems such as flow capacity or pumping rates during the transmission of various fluids, regardless of their types. The change in viscosity causes certain problems. One of the most efficient methods used to solve this problem is called blending. The purpose of this method is to reduce the overall apparent viscosity of the well fluid. To achieve this,

light crude oils, natural gas liquids, chemical additives, and so on are usually used (Petter, 2012). Blending can be conducted in-tank (Batch) or in-line. In the first process, fluids with different viscosities are stored in separate tanks and then are mixed in another tank until a homogeneous solution is obtained. Subsequently, the solution is used for the other operations. In another way, different crude oils from separate lines are collected in a certain tank after passing through the mixing device and put to use.

Experimental part:

In this part of the thesis, we will discuss the experiment that was conducted. The aim of the experiment is to bring an innovation to the viscosity blending method by using biofuel. The substances needed during the experiment were biofuel (100 ml) and heavy oil (total 900 ml), which have different viscosities. The expected result of the experiment was to reduce total viscosity of the mixture prepared with heavy oil and biofuel, when the concentration of biofuel is raised. The main equipment in the experiment was the Brookfield DV2T viscometer. In general, solutions with 6 different concentrations (5%, 15%, 25%, 35%, 45%, 50%) should be prepared. The biofuel was prepared in a chemical laboratory by using banana peel as catalysts, and wasted cooking sunflower oil. Since the amount of biofuel was limited here, it was possible to obtain concentrations by increasing the amount of heavy oil. The experiment was conducted at the room temperature (approximately 20-22 °C), and the viscometer indicators were set to 100 rpm speed, 20 seconds by utilizing spindle G3. The viscosity of each solution was measured and recorded in the viscometer data base. After measuring a certain solution, it is necessary to pay attention to cleaning the viscometer spindle so that inaccuracy does not occur during measurements. As mentioned before, the viscosity of each mixture was measured. Finally, using the obtained data, a plot of viscosity versus concentration was drawn in Excel (Graph 1). From the trend of the figure, it is seen that as the concentration of biofuel in the solution increases, the viscosity of the mixture decreases, and this represents the confirmation of the purpose of the experiment.

Graph 1: Dependency of the viscosity on the concentration of the biofuel

Results and discussion:

Using biofuels in viscosity blending offers several advantages. Starting with the main purpose of viscosity blending, which is decreasing the viscosity of heavy oils, biofuels are capable to reduce

the viscosity (Cohen). Since they are in most cases oxygenated compounds, their viscosity is tent to be lower than the heavy oils'. Mostly, light hydrocarbons are utilized to fulfil this process, however usage of hydrocarbons minimizes the dependency on non-renewable resources. Biofuels can successfully reduce the viscosity and improve flowability. By doing so, they can make pumping procedure easier, protect pipelines from blockages and enhance the lifespan of the pipeline (Demirbas, 2008). They have better lubricating ability that helps to decrease wear or tear in pipelines and pumps. The best side of biofuels are that they are completely renewable. For example, components of the biofuel used in the experimentation (Experimental part) are quite common in the nature. Sunflower oil whether used or fresh is widely available. So does banana peel. That is why, production of biofuels is not expensive. Apart from these, biofuels are more environmentally friendly. They cause lower carbon dioxide emissions and sulfur content. They also break down naturally, which is important in terms of environmental contamination.

Naturally, it is normal for biofuel use to face restrictions in the oil industry. In our proposed conditions, these emerging technical, chemical, and economic problems have been prevented or it is possible to see that there is a certain solution. Biofuels have the property of solidification at low temperatures, which can cause the pipe to be blocked by solidification in oil pipelines. Still, considering that the physical properties of the sunflower-banana mixture we produce have a freezing temperature between -10 and 0 degrees, this does not cause problems in pipelines in the climatic conditions of Azerbaijan. Another problem is that pipelines that have been designed for oil products for many years and are structurally adapted to the properties of oil may require changes in the absorption of biofuel (Handwerk, 2007). Biofuels applied to old pipes, which contain oxygen, can accelerate corrosion in a way. Additionally, high percentage of oxygen increases the possibility of spontaneous combustion in oil pipes coming under high pressure. However, as mentioned above, the absorption of stabilizers such as BHT and TBHQ will reduce the risk of this corrosion and combustion (Makogon, 2019). The BHT stabilizer can maintain the stability of biofuel for at least 3 months, and even in the optimal situation, this can be extended to 7-8 months (Parlak, 2023). Knowing that the pipelines are constantly monitored, and regularly reviewing the risk of ignition will eliminate this obstacle. Also, in this method, we propose, that banana peel, a component of biofuel production, performs the function of preventing the acidity of free oils in the pipes and corrosion of the pipes. Methanol and sodium hydroxide can neutralize this acidity.

Another important difficulty is the problem of phase separation of the oil and biofuel mixture, but these solutions are in the form of a homogeneous mixture. BHT stabilizer also ensures phase separation and the separation is minimal in the 10%-35% biofuel composition. In addition, static mixers and inline sensors can provide the necessary mixing.

The economic problem of obtaining biofuels and additional stabilizers is the transportation and production costs. However, an energy-saving solution is to reuse used vegetable oils and banana peels, which do not need to go through any processing procedure. As an alternative solution, biofuel production near onshore oil fields will reduce transportation costs in another aspect (Yasser, 2004).

Offers:

Biofuels can be considered as an option for viscosity blending, since they are renewable and eco-friendly. If the procedure is carried out with them, there is 85% less CO_2 emissions. (Atadashi, 2010) They break down easily and faster than any light oil, which reduces time and energy needed for the process. (Hanna, 1999) Biofuels are non-toxic, it is an advantage in terms of safety. One of the best advantages is that after they are blended with heavy oils and transportation is done, resulting waste oils are going to be less and even they can be treated easily. Additionally, biofuels are cost-effective method to decrease viscosity of heavy oils successfully. However, there are some cons that make their application an issue. As mentioned before biofuels contain oxygen inside them that can result in oxidation reactions inside the pipes. For this problem, BHT and TBHQ stabilizers are offered to be used in order to reduce the risk of both combustion and corrosion. The phase separation problem

can also be solved with the help of stabilizers. Another downside is the solidification characteristics of biofuels, which occurs in between -10-0 degrees, is not a big issue considering the climate of Azerbaijan. Since reasonable solutions can be advised and applied for disadvantages of biofuels, it is safe to say that they can be offered to be used in petroleum industry to decrease the viscosity of heavy oils when it is needed.

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